

MELATONIN PROTECTS AGAINST OXIDATIVE DAMAGE IN SPLEEN AND DETERIORATION OF IMMUNE FUNCTION IN FORCED SWIM-STRESSED LABORATORY MICE

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ABSTRACT. Stress is an external or internal stimulus that interferes with the normal physiology and homeostatic status of an individual. Acute stress is the short-term exposure to stress and chronic stress involves prolonged exposure to stress. Forced swimming stress is a widely accepted model to study physiological stress in laboratory animals. Melatonin is a powerful antioxidant and modulator of the immune system. Melatonin modulates physiological activities through its high-affinity MT1 and MT2 receptors and directly through scavenging free radicals. The present study evaluated the involvement of melatonin in the attenuation of forced swimming stressed induced oxidative stress, splenocyte proliferation, intracellular ROS generation, and phagocytic index of macrophages. Acute and chronic swimming stress caused an increase in lipid peroxidation and reduced the antioxidant enzyme (SOD and catalase) activity in the spleen of mice. Melatonin supplementation to both chronic and acute stressed groups decreased lipid peroxidation and enhanced the antioxidant activity (SOD and catalase) in the spleen of mice. Melatonin attenuated the suppression of phagocytic activity, and splenocyte proliferation caused by both acute and chronic swim stress. Swim stress caused increased MT1 and MT2 receptor expression in the spleen of mice. Increased expression of melatonin receptors might be responsible for melatonin-mediated induction of antioxidant enzyme activity during stressed conditions in mice. Therefore, the present study may suggest that melatonin attenuates the swim-stressed induced oxidative stress, and suppression of immune functions through modulation of MT1 and MT2 receptors.

Keywords: *Forced swimming stress, melatonin, spleen, oxidative stress, MT1 & MT2 receptors.*

INTRODUCTION

Forced swimming stress developed by Porsolt et al. [1] is considered to be an adverse stimulus, which can be used as an experimental model to induce physiological stress in laboratory animals [2]. Swimming is not always a simple exercise, as elimination of emotional factors is difficult [3, 4]. In small laboratory animals, forced swimming test has been widely used for studying the physiological changes and the capability of the organism to respond to the generated stressful condition [5, 6].

Proper functioning of the immune system is ideal for maintaining good animal health; however, several factors including stress has either positive or negative impact on immune system [7]. Evidence suggested that chronic stress results in immunosuppression in human and animal models [8, 9]. The pathophysiology of tissue macrophages is studied

by using peritoneal macrophages [10]. Collection of peritoneal fluid from rodents has been a well-established technique for isolating macrophages [11]. Spleen, the largest secondary immune organ is responsible for initiating immune reactions to blood-borne antigens and for filtering the blood of foreign material and old or damaged red blood cells. The intensity and duration of stress exposure also determines immunologic induction or suppression which may be correlated to ROS generation in peritoneal macrophages and spleen lymphocytes [12]. It has been reported that exposure to stressful situations stimulates numerous pathways which lead to increased production of oxygen free radicals [13]. Excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) leads to damage to spleen tissues. Oxidative stress reflects an imbalance between the systematic manifestation of reactive oxygen species and the biological system's ability to readily detoxify the reactive intermediates or to repair the resulting damage. Lipid peroxidation is one of the major consequences induced by oxidative stress. Antioxidants remove excess ROS from the cells and thus protect the body from detrimental effects generated by ROS [14]. Enzymatic antioxidant SOD neutralizes superoxide anion to molecular oxygen and hydrogen peroxide [15], whereas catalase neutralizes hydrogen peroxide to molecular oxygen and water in living tissue [16].

Melatonin, a known immune modulator has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties [17]. Melatonin has been found to be a direct free radical scavenger of oxygen radicals. Melatonin promotes expression of different antioxidant enzymes which includes superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione reductase, and catalase through melatonin receptors [18, 19]. It has been reported that high-affinity melatonin receptors were localized on circulating lymphocytes in rodents, chickens and humans [20, 21]. Melatonin receptors has been found to localized in splenocytes of humans, rodents and birds [22, 23]. Melatonin protects tissues and organs from reactive oxygen species generated by various stresses. Studies suggested the protective action of melatonin against oxidative stress caused by several stressors but scanty reports suggest the responsiveness of MT1 and MT2 receptors in melatonin-mediated protection against physiological stress. Therefore, the present study investigated the protective effect of melatonin and the responsiveness of MT1 and MT2 receptors against forced swim stress-induced oxidative stress and altered immune functions in laboratory mice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animal maintenance and experiments with animals were done following the institutional practice and within the framework of CPCSEA (Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experimental Animals) and the Act of Government of India (2007) for animal welfare.

Animal Model

Swiss Albino Mice colonies were maintained in standard laboratory environment, maintaining proper light with 12 hours light and 12 hrs dark, temperature ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and humidity ($55\pm 5\%$). Five mice were kept in each group and feed with mice food and water *ad libitum*. Male mice (25g) body weight was selected for the experimental purpose.

Forced Swimming Stress

Mice were exposed to forced swimming daily for a duration of 15 minutes, between 11.30 a.m. to 11.45 a.m. for 30 days. They were forced to swim in a big jar (24 cm diameter x 30cm height) containing tap water. The depth of water in the jar was 15 cm.

Experimental Design

Healthy male mice were selected and randomly divided into 5 groups, each group containing five mice. Mice received treatment as follows- Group 1, Control (Con) mice were given ethanolic saline. Group 2, acute swimming stress (AS), mice were subjected to swim for 15 minutes prior to dissection. Group 3, chronic swimming stress (CS), mice were subjected to chronic stress by allowing the mice to swim for 15 minutes daily for continuous 30 days. Group 4, acute swimming stress along with melatonin treatment (AS+M), mice were given melatonin treatment for 30 continuous days and then they were allowed to swim for 15 minutes on the next day after the completion of melatonin treatment (25µg/100g body weight/day). Group 5, chronic swimming stress (CS+M) mice were given melatonin (25µg/100g body weight/day) treatment for 30 continuous days and then they were allowed to swim for 15 minutes daily for 30 days. After 24hrs of the last treatment mice were sacrificed by decapitation. Peritoneal macrophages were collected and the spleen was dissected. The spleen of individual mice was processed for oxidative stress analysis, splenocyte culture, immunohistochemistry, RNA isolation, and reverse transcription PCR.

Determination of lipid peroxidation level in spleen

A by-product of lipid peroxidation is Malondialdehyde (MDA), measured on the basis of its reaction with TBA (Thiobarbituric acid). The MDA assay was done by following the method of Okhawa et al. [24]. Phosphate Buffer was used to make 10% tissue homogenate. 3.3 ml TBA reagent [containing 8% SDS, 20% acetic acid (pH 3.5), 0.8% TBA, and 0.8% butylated hydroxyl-toluene] was added to 0.1ml of tissue homogenate. After boiling the reaction mixture, centrifugation was done and optical density was determined at 532nm wavelength. Lipid peroxidation was calculated in nmol TBARS formed/mg protein.

Evaluation of superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity level in spleen

Superoxide dismutase (SOD; EC 1.15.1.1) activity in the spleen of experimental mice was determined by following the method of Das et al. (2000) [25] in splenic tissue of experimental mice. 10% homogenates of the spleen tissues were prepared in phosphate-buffered saline (pH=7.4). In a test tube, 0.1 ml of the homogenate was added. 1.4 ml of the reaction mixture [containing 50mM phosphate buffer (pH, 7.4), 20 mM L-methionine, 1% Triton-X-100, 10 mM hydroxylamine hydrochloride, 50 mM EDTA] was added to the tissue homogenate. Riboflavin was added before exposing the test tubes to 20W fluorescence lamp. Griess reagent (1 ml) was added and optical density was measured at 543 nm.

Evaluation of catalase (CAT) activity level in spleen

Catalase (CAT; EC 1.11.1.6) activity was done by following the method of Sinha (1972) [26], modified by Hadwan (2016) [27]. Preparation of 10% homogenate of the

spleen was done in phosphate buffer (pH=7.4). The supernatant was added to a reaction mixture containing H₂O₂ and H₂O. Potassium dichromate was added and boiled in a water bath followed by centrifugation. The optical density was determined at 570 nm. The activity of CAT was expressed as the amount of H₂O₂ degraded per minute.

Isolation of Peritoneal Leukocytes

After euthanization, 70% alcohol was sprayed over the abdominal region of the mice and a small incision was made on outer skin to expose the inner skin of the peritoneal cavity. A 25 gauge needle was used to inject 5 ml of sterilized PBS (Phosphate buffered Saline) in the peritoneal cavity. After gently tabbing the mice abdominal region, nearly 5 ml of peritoneal fluid was withdrawn by using a 22 gauge needle. The peritoneal fluid was centrifuged and the pellet was washed with PBS for twice. The pellet was suspended in 10% FCS containing culture medium.

Measurement of Intracellular ROS

Measurement of intracellular ROS was done by following the methods of Majewski et al. (2005) [28]. Peritoneal leukocytes plated in 96 well culture plates (10⁶ cells/well) were kept in 5% CO₂ incubator at 37°C for 1 hour. Non adherent cells were washed with PBS, 100µl NBT (1mg/ml) was added to each well and incubated for another 1 hour. After discarding the medium, 70% methanol was used for cell fixation and washed with PBS. 120µl of KOH and 140µl of DMSO (Dimethyl sulphoxide) were added to dissolve the formazan crystals in each well. The amount of formazans was measured by reading the absorbance at 630 nm UV-vis spectrophotometer.

Preparation of macrophage monolayer

The peritoneal leukocytes were flooded on pre-washed slides and placed in 5% CO₂ incubator at 37°C for 2 hrs. After two hrs supernatant was discarded and slides were washed with PBS and processed for phagocytic study.

Preparation of Yeast Cell Suspension

A solution of commercial Baker's yeast (3mg/ml) was prepared in PBS (pH= 7.8). The solution was warmed at 80°C for 15 minutes. The solution was washed and resuspended in a complete culture medium.

Phagocytic Assay

Phagocytic assay of macrophage was done by the method of Roy and Rai (2008) [29]. Yeast cell suspension was heated for 15 minutes and the macrophage monolayer was flooded with the suspension. After incubation for 90 minutes, yeast suspension was removed by PBS and the slides were fixed with methanol. Giemsa staining was done and macrophages were counted randomly under light microscope. Numbers of phagocytic cells were counted in 100 cells to determine the percent phagocytosis.

Splenocyte Proliferation

Single-cell suspension of splenocytes was prepared in PBS. Erythrocytes of splenic cell suspension were lysed with Tris-NH₄Cl (pH 7.2) and washed with PBS. Cell viability was determined and the number was adjusted to 1x10⁷ cells/ml in culture. 100µl

splenocytes suspension was added to the wells of sterile flat bottom 96 well culture plates. The splenocyte culture was stimulated with T cell mitogen concanavalin A. Culture plate was incubated in a humidified 5% CO₂-containing chamber at 37°C for 44 hrs. 20µl MTT solution was mixed in each well and incubated for another 4 hours. After completion of the incubation period, 100µl of acidified propanol was added and the optical density was measured at 570 nm wavelength by using a microplate reader (ECIL, India) [22]. For statistical analysis, mean OD values for each set of duplicates were used. Percent stimulation index was determined from the ratio of absorbance of the mitogen-stimulated cultures to control cultures.

Immunohistochemistry

Immunohistochemical localization of MT1 and MT2 receptor proteins was done in the spleen of experimental mice following the modified methods of Singh et al. [30]. 5µm thick spleen section was mounted on a gelatin-coated slide. Antibodies against MT1 and MT2 receptors protein were used for the detection of respective receptors. Antigen-antibody interaction was visualized by the HRP enzyme-catalyzed DAB+H₂O₂ reaction.

RNA Isolation, cDNA synthesis and PCR

The total RNA of the spleen was isolated by using PureZol (Biorad, USA) and cDNA was synthesized by using iScript cDNA synthesis kit (Biorad, USA). The cDNA was amplified by using specific forward and reverse primer of MT1 (Forward 5'-CCGGAACACTCCAGTACGAT-3' and reverse 5'-GGACCAGGACCCATATCCTT-3' give 150 bp PCR product), MT2 (Forward 5'-TTTATGGGTCCTGACCAG-3' and reverse 5'-CCCTGTCGCTCCTCAGTAAG-3' give 121bp PCR product) and GAPDH (Forward 5'-AACTTTGGCATTGTGGAAGG-3' and reverse 5'-ACACATTGGGGGTAGGAACA-3' give 132 bp PCR product). MT1 & MT2 Receptor expression was done in terms of optical density in comparison to GAPDH.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was done using SPSS 17.0 (SPSS Corp., USA) program with one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple range tests for multiple comparisons. The differences were considered significant when $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of swimming stress on Lipid Peroxidation (MDA level)

Significant ($p < 0.01$) increased MDA level was noted in the spleen of acute and chronic stressed groups of mice as compared to the spleen of the control group. Melatonin supplementation in both chronic and acute stressed groups significantly ($p < 0.01$) decreased the MDA level in the spleen of mice compared to the respective stressed groups (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on lipid peroxidation (MDA level) in spleen tissue of laboratory mice. Histograms represent Mean \pm SEM, $n=5$ for each group. Con = control, CS = Chronic stress, CS+M = Chronic stress + melatonin, AS = Acute stress, AS+M = Acute stress + melatonin. ** $p<0.01$, Con vs CS, Con vs AS; ## $p<0.01$, CS vs CS+M, AS vs AS+M.

Effect of swimming stress on Superoxide Dismutase Enzyme Activity

Both chronic and acute swimming stress significantly ($p<0.01$) suppressed the SOD enzyme activity in the spleen compared to the control group of mice. Melatonin supplementation caused a significant ($p<0.01$) increase in the SOD enzyme activity in chronic as well as acute groups of mice compared to respective stressed groups (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) activity (U/mg protein) in spleen tissue of laboratory mice. Histogram represents Mean \pm SEM, $n=5$ for each group. Con = control, CS = Chronic stress, CS+M = Chronic stress + melatonin, AS = Acute stress, AS+M = Acute stress + melatonin. ** $p<0.01$, Con vs CS, Con vs AS; ## $p<0.01$, CS vs CS+M, AS vs AS+M.

Effect of swimming stress on Catalase Enzyme Activity

Significantly ($p < 0.01$) suppressed catalase activity was noted in the spleen of both chronic and acute swimming stress groups compared to the control group of mice. Melatonin supplementation in chronic and acute swimming stressed groups caused a significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in the catalase enzyme activity in the spleen as compared to respective stressed groups of mice (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on Catalase activity (kU/mg protein) in spleen tissue of laboratory mice. Histogram represents Mean \pm SEM, $n=5$ for each group. Con = control, CS = Chronic stress, CS+M = Chronic stress + melatonin, AS = Acute stress, AS+M = Acute stress + melatonin. ** $p < 0.01$, Con vs CS, Con vs AS; ## $p < 0.01$, CS vs CS+M, AS vs AS+M.

Effect of swimming stress on cellular ROS of peritoneal macrophages

Intracellular ROS generation in peritoneal macrophages can be measured by the amount of NBT converted to water-insoluble blue formazan crystal by superoxide anions. A significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in intracellular ROS level was noted in peritoneal leukocytes of both chronic and acute stress groups of mice compared to the control group. The acute stress group of mice showed significantly ($p < 0.01$) increased ROS levels than the chronic stress group of mice. Melatonin supplementation to both chronic and acute stressed mice showed significant suppression of the ROS levels in peritoneal leukocytes in comparison with respective stress groups of mice (Fig. 4).

Effect of swimming stress on the phagocytic index of macrophages

Phagocytic activity was assessed by the number of yeast cells phagocytosed by the peritoneal macrophages. Significant ($p < 0.01$) suppression in the phagocytic index of peritoneal macrophages was noted in both chronic as well as acute stressed mice in comparison to the control group of mice. Significantly ($p < 0.01$) suppressed phagocytic index was seen in the acute stress group of mice compared to the chronic stress group of mice. Melatonin supplementation caused a significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in the phagocytic index of peritoneal macrophages in both chronic and acute stressed mice (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on intracellular ROS level (NBT assay) in peritoneal leukocytes of laboratory mice. Histogram represents Mean \pm SEM, $n=5$ for each group. Con = control, CS = Chronic stress, CS+M = Chronic stress + melatonin, AS = Acute stress, AS+M = Acute stress + melatonin. ** $p<0.01$, Con vs CS, Con vs AS; ## $p<0.01$, CS vs CS+M, AS vs AS+M.

Fig. 5. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on % Phagocytosis in peritoneal leukocytes of laboratory mice. Histogram represents Mean \pm SEM, $n=5$ for each group. Con = control, CS = Chronic stress, CS+M = Chronic stress + melatonin, AS = Acute stress, AS+M = Acute stress + melatonin. ** $p<0.01$, Con vs CS, Con vs AS; ## $p<0.01$, CS vs CS+M, AS vs AS+M.

Effect of swimming stress on splenocytes proliferation

Both the chronic and acute swimming stress significantly ($p<0.01$) suppressed the splenocyte proliferation in experimental mice in comparison to the control group of mice. Melatonin supplementation to both chronic stress and acute stress groups of mice caused a significant ($p<0.01$) increase in splenocyte proliferation in comparison to respective stress groups (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on % Stimulation Ratio (MTT assay) of splenocytes of laboratory mice. Histogram represents Mean \pm SEM, $n=5$ for each group. Con = control, CS = Chronic stress, CS+M = Chronic stress + melatonin, AS = Acute stress, AS+M = Acute stress + melatonin. ** $p<0.01$, Con vs CS, Con vs AS; ## $p<0.01$, CS vs CS+M, AS vs AS+M.

Fig. 7. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on the immunoreactivity of MT1 receptor antisera in spleen of laboratory mice. A = control, B = Chronic stress, C = Chronic stress + melatonin, D = Acute stress, E = Acute stress + melatonin.

Immunohistochemical observations

Immunoreactivity of MT1 receptor antisera was noted in the spleen of the control group of mice. Both chronic and acute swimming-stressed groups of mice showed strong immunoreactivity of MT1 receptor antisera in the spleen of mice. Melatonin supplementation to chronic as well as acute swimming-stressed mice showed stronger immunoreactivity of MT1 receptor in comparison to respective stress groups of mice (Fig. 7).

Immunoreactivity of MT2 receptor antisera was noted in the spleen of the control group of mice. Chronic swimming-stressed mice groups showed strong MT2 receptor antisera immunoreactivity in the spleen of mice. The acute stress group of mice showed normal immunoreactivity of MT2 receptor antisera. Melatonin treatment induces stronger immunoreactivity of MT2 antisera in the spleen of experimental mice (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on the immunoreactivity of MT2 receptor antisera in spleen of laboratory mice. A = control, B = Chronic stress, C = Chronic stress + melatonin, D = Acute stress, E = Acute stress + melatonin.

Receptor mRNA expression

Reverse transcription PCR showed a significant ($p < 0.01$) increase of MT1 receptor mRNA expression in both acute and chronic swimming-stressed mice groups in comparison with the control group of mice. Melatonin supplemented to chronic stressed

and acute stressed mice showed significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased expression of MT1 receptors in comparison to the chronic and acute stressed group of mice (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on MT1 mRNA expression in spleen of laboratory mice. Histogram represents Mean \pm SEM, $n=5$ for each group. Con = control, CS = Chronic stress, CS+M = Chronic stress + melatonin, AS = Acute stress, AS+M = Acute stress + melatonin. ** $p < 0.01$, Con vs CS, Con vs AS; # $p < 0.05$, CS vs CS+M, AS vs AS+M.

The chronic stress mice showed a significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in MT2 receptor mRNA expression in spleen tissue compared to the control group of mice. Acute stress could not bring any change in MT2 receptor mRNA expression in spleen tissue. Melatonin treatment caused a significant ($p < 0.01$ in the chronic stress group and $p < 0.05$ in the acute stress group) increase in MT2 receptor mRNA expression in spleen tissue compared to the respective stress groups of mice (Fig 10).

Swimming stress developed by Porsolt et al. [1] is a widely accepted model for studying physical stress in laboratory animals. Forced swimming stress induces neurochemical, endocrine, and immune alterations that occur in a time-dependent manner after exposure to stress [31]. Both acute and chronic stress lead to the generation of reactive oxygen species which results in an imbalance between the antioxidant enzymes and the ROS generated in the body [32].

Fig. 10. Effect of acute and chronic swim stress on MT2 mRNA expression in spleen of laboratory mice. Histogram represents Mean \pm SEM, $n=5$ for each group. Con = control, CS = Chronic stress, CS+M = Chronic stress + melatonin, AS = Acute stress, AS+M = Acute stress + melatonin. ** $p<0.01$, Con vs CS, Con vs AS; # $p<0.05$, AS vs AS+M, ## $p<0.01$, CS vs CS + M.

Lipid peroxidation is a fundamental event of oxidative stress and free radical production [33]. We have noted increased MDA levels in the spleen of chronically stressed and acutely stressed mice compared to the control. Studies suggested that repeated exposure to swimming stress generated free radicals and caused an increase of lipid peroxidation in the liver, kidney, and brain tissues [34]. Melatonin supplementation to both the chronic and acute stressed group reduced the MDA level in the spleen of mice. Previous studies suggest that melatonin administration inhibited swimming stress-induced increase of MDA levels in various tissues of rats [35]. SOD is an antioxidant enzyme that scavenges the superoxide anion by converting this free radical to oxygen and hydrogen peroxide [15]. Catalase is an antioxidant enzyme that catalyzes the conversion of hydrogen peroxide to water and molecular oxygen [16]. SOD and catalase enzyme activity was decreased in both acute and chronic forced swimming stressed mice as compared to the control mice. Decreased superoxide dismutase enzyme was observed in the liver and skeletal muscle of rats exposed to forced swimming stress [36] and a significant decrease in catalase level was noted in the brain of mice exposed to forced swimming stress [37]. Melatonin administration caused an increase in the SOD and catalase activities in both acute and chronically stressed mice. Studies suggested that

melatonin increases the antioxidant enzyme activity in the spleen tissues of hyperglycaemic mice [38].

In present study, increased intracellular ROS level was noted in peritoneal leukocytes of both chronic stressed and acute stressed mice. Acute swimming stressed mice showed significant higher ROS level than chronic stressed mice. Melatonin supplementation to both chronic and acute stressed mice significantly suppressed the ROS level in peritoneal leukocytes. A significant suppression of phagocytosis of peritoneal macrophages was noted in both chronic and acute stressed mice groups compared to the control group of mice. The swimming stress-induced elevation of intracellular ROS generation might be the reason for the suppression of the phagocytic activity of peritoneal macrophages in both stressed groups. Melatonin supplementation to both chronic and acute stressed groups suppressed the intracellular ROS generation and thus increased the phagocytic activity of peritoneal macrophages. The report suggested that melatonin supplementation reduced the glycaemic stress-induced ROS in peritoneal macrophages and significantly increased the phagocytic index in diabetic mice [39]. Both chronic and acute swim stress significantly suppressed splenocyte proliferation in experimental mice. Although moderate exercises are observed to have beneficial effects on an organism, however, long-term exposure to such stressors may have detrimental effects on the immune status of the organism [12]. Melatonin supplementation to both the chronic and acute stressed group enhanced splenocyte proliferation. Earlier studies suggested that melatonin supplementation attenuated glycaemic stress and enhanced splenocyte proliferation in diabetic mice [38].

Both chronic and acute stress caused increased MT1 and MT2 receptor immunoreactivity in the experimental mice, whereas melatonin supplementation induces MT1 and MT2 receptor immunoreactivity in both acute and chronic stressed groups of mice. Melatonin supplementation to the acute stress group showed the strongest MT1 receptor immunoreactivity, whereas melatonin supplemented to the chronic stress group showed the strongest MT2 receptor immunoreactivity among the other experimental groups. Reverse transcription PCR data also showed that chronic and acute stress significantly increased MT1 receptor mRNA levels in experimental mice whereas, melatonin supplementation caused an increase of MT1 and MT2 receptor mRNA levels in spleen tissue of both acute and chronic stressed groups of mice. Earlier studies showed an increase of MT1 and MT2 receptors in the kidney tissue of arsenic-stressed mice [40]. Melatonin treatment caused an increase in MT2 receptor protein expression in the spleen tissue of heat-stressed mice [23]. Further, PCR analysis suggested an increase in MT1 and MT2 receptor expression in the kidney tissue of arsenic-stressed mice [40].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our results showed that forced swimming stress led to the generation of oxidative stress in the spleen of mice. Melatonin being a powerful antioxidant helps in ameliorating the forced swimming stress-induced oxidative stress. Forced swimming stress also caused a decreased phagocytic activity of peritoneal macrophages and suppressed splenocyte proliferation and thus suppressed the immune function in both acute and chronically stressed groups. Melatonin supplementation ameliorated the swim stress-induced oxidative stress in spleen tissues and increased the phagocytic activity of peritoneal macrophages and splenocyte proliferation in experimental mice. Expression patterns of MT1 and MT2 receptors in spleen tissues of both acute and chronic swim-

stressed mice may suggest differential activation of MT1 and MT2 receptors in melatonin-mediated protection from forced swimming stress in studied mice.

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